

NR613: New BV Rules for Bonded Assemblies

Stéphane Paboef^{1,*}, Maxime Deydier¹, Benjamin Collier¹, Jean-Christophe Petiteau¹ and Marie-Odette Quéméré¹

¹ Bureau Veritas, Research Department, Saint-Herblain, France

Abstract. Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from marine and offshore industries are regulated by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), with increasingly stringent criteria aimed at achieving zero emissions by 2050. The use of lightweight materials such as composites can significantly reduce the weight of ships and offshore structures, resulting in lower fuel consumption and associated emissions throughout their operational lifespan. However, the assembly of hybrid structures combining metallic and composite components presents challenges due to the lack of robust methodologies for assessing the integrity of bonded joints. Traditional stress-based design approaches cannot be applied to all applications. To address this gap, Bureau Veritas (BV) has recently developed a new rule note for bonded assemblies of composites and multi-materials structures. The rule outlines a comprehensive methodology for evaluating bonded joint based on a qualification programme dependent on the safety class and maturity level of the assembly. Three distinct justification methods can be applied for the strength validation: (i) Method A - Design justified by tests only, all parameters (materials, shape, loading point) of the designed assembly part are always the same; (ii) Method B - Design justified by calculations only, can be only used for low qualification levels; (iii) Method C - Design justified by tests and calculations, whatever the qualification level. This paper describes the content and application of BV NR613 Rules for Bonded Assemblies, detailing three bonded assembly case studies that demonstrate the implementation of the three justification methods. The case studies provide practical examples of the industrial application of the new rules.

Keywords: *bonding, adhesive, qualification.*

1. Introduction

Special processes, such as welding or bonding, are defined by ISO 9001 as the products or production steps where the resulting output cannot be fully verified by subsequent monitoring or measurement. As shown in Figure 1 (left), if there is a risk of error, it should be mitigated by implementing a comprehensive quality management system throughout the manufacturing process. Although often criticized, this is precisely the approach adopted by the ISO 9001 standard.

In the case of adhesive bonding, even if the adhesive itself is assumed to be defect-free, ensuring product quality requires eliminating errors at every stage of the manufacturing process. However, in practice, the quality assurance of a product or a production includes the technical quality assurance and the organizational quality assurance as illustrated in Figure 1 (right). Technical quality assurance addresses uncertainties related to the process itself, covering aspects such as test protocols, experimental data, and test specimens. Organizational quality assurance, on the other hand, focuses on mitigating uncertainties arising from organizational factors, including compliance with relevant standards, regulations, specifications, as well as personnel, equipment, and facilities.

While ISO 9001 specifies the minimum requirements for a certified quality management system, it remains not sufficient in the scope of the classification of bonded assemblies for marine and offshore structures. To address this issue, Bureau Veritas has developed a new rule note NR613 [1], which provides additional quality requirements for bonded assemblies. Bonded assemblies are subjected to the Bonding Specification provided by the shipyard and considering the following technical items:

- Description of the considered assembly
- Application and function of the assembly
- Location of the bonded assembly on-board
- Loads to be withstood by the assembly
- Bonded assembly maturity

* Correspondence to: stephane.paboef@bureauveritas.com

- Safety class
- Qualification requirement level
- Characteristics of the adhesive
- Surface conditions of materials to be assembled
- Production process and limitations
- Bonder qualification
- Operations after curing that could impair bonding application

Furthermore, the design is to be assessed in accordance with technical regulations of NR613 and the bonding process must be supervised by a Bonding Coordinator.

Figure 1. Standard process quality management, - ISO9001 concept (left) & Special process such as adhesive bonding - DIN2304 concept (right) [2]

The rule note NR613 for Bonded Assemblies is composed of 5 sections giving: (i) the scope of application of the note, (ii) the methodology for the assessment of a bonded assembly, detailed in the present paper, (iii) the tests to be performed for the characterization of the assembly and for the certification of the adhesive, (iv) the design requirements based on 3 justification methods presented hereafter, and (v) the manufacturing requirements to ensure the quality of the bonding joint. The paper describes the methodology for the determination of the qualification programme and detailed the 3 justification methods to assess the design of bonded assemblies. Then, justification methods are illustrated by 3 industrial application cases.

2. Bonded Assembly Methodology Assessment

As described in NR613 [1], the methodology for assessing a bonded assembly is composed of six main steps:

- Bonding specification and qualification level: defining the bonded assembly
- Bonding qualification program: based on qualification levels
- Bonded assembly design file: gathering all design information
- Shipyard/Manufacturer preliminary review: including documentation stage, preliminary survey, review report
- Manufacturing, Testing and Inspection (MTI) Bonding plan
- Manufacturing

The following sections present the Safety Class and Maturity Level used to determine the Qualification Level leading to the Qualification Program applied for each bonded assembly to be qualified.

2.1. Safety Class

Safety Classes have been defined to assess the criticality of the bonded assembly in case of failure. Safety class varies from SC 1, low level, to SC 3, high level, as defined in Table 1.

Table 1. Safety Class

Safety Class		Definition
SC 1	Low level	Failure of the bonded assembly will result in a failure of a function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • which will not affect an essential service • which will not lead to dangerous situations for human safety, safety of the ship and/or threat to the environment
SC 2	Medium level	Failure of the bonded assembly will result in a failure of a function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • which could eventually affect an essential service • which could eventually lead to dangerous situations for human safety, safety of the ship and/or threat to the environment
SC 3	High level	Failure of the bonded assembly will result in a failure of a function: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • which could immediately affect an essential service • which could immediately lead to dangerous situations for human safety, safety of the ship and/or threat to the environment

2.2. Maturity level

The bonded assembly maturity level is to be determined in accordance with Table 2, taking into account the bonded assembly configuration, materials, processes and shipyard/manufacturer experience.

The maturity of a bonded assembly could be evidenced by a design of joint that has been already used on-board a ship with the same design, material, multiple conditions of application and for a period of more than 5 years so that in service feedback can be documented and submitted to the Society.

Table 2. Maturity level

Maturity level	Proof of maturity	
1	Proven	Documented operational references with the applicable conditions of operation
2	Limited reference	Few or short operational references
3	Unproven	New bonded assembly without any reference

2.3. Qualification level

The qualification level of the bonded assembly is determined in accordance with Table 3.

Table 3. Qualification level

			Maturity level		
			Proven	Limited reference	Unproven
			1	2	3
Safety Class	Low level	SC 1	Q1	Q2	Q2
	Medium level	SC 2	Q2	Q3	Q4
	High level	SC 3	Q3	Q4	Q5

2.4. Qualification program

The qualification program specifying the qualification requirements depending on the qualification level is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Qualification programme

Qualification requirements	Qualification level			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Adhesive Type Approval Certificate	-	-	X	X
Bonded Assembly characterization	-	X	X	X
Ageing	-	-	X	X
Adhesive protection	-	-	X	X
Strength validation by justification method	A, B or C	A, B or C	A or C	A or C
Creep	-	-	-	X
Fatigue	-	-	-	X
Manufacturing	Control of the environment	X	X	X
	Traceability of materials	-	X	X
	Traceability of process	-	-	X
	Qualification of bonders	-	-	-
Survey/Structural Health Monitoring	-	-	X	X

Note: - = Not Applicable; X = Mandatory

When a bonded assembly has a Qualification level Q1, the 3 justification methods A, B or C can be applied for assessing the design and only the control of the environment during the manufacturing is required. Whereas for a Qualification level Q4, all qualification requirements are required and only justification methods A or C can be used. Bonded assembly ranked Q5 has at least Q4 qualification requirements and additional justifications could be required on a case-by-case basis.

3. Justification methods

The strength of a bonded assembly is to be demonstrated in all combinations of loads described in the applicable rules. This assessment is to be carried out by using one of the three justification methods, see Figure 2, that are proposed in NR613 [1] and described hereafter:

- Method A - Design justified by tests only
All parameters (materials, shape, loading point) of the designed assembly part are always the same. Method A can be applied whatever the qualification level.
- Method B - Design justified by calculations only
Method B can be only used for qualification levels Q1 and Q2 with a justification of adhesive properties.
- Method C - Design justified by tests and calculations
Method C can be applied whatever the qualification level.

Figure 2. Justification methods A, B and C

3.1. Method A

Method A is applied when the design is fixed (i.e. no thickness variation, no geometry variation, no material variation), and whatever the qualification level. The strength of the bonded assembly is to be demonstrated by representative tests performed at full scale or in representative configuration agreed with the Society. For the assembly validation, all load cases are to fulfil the following formula (1):

$$L_{design}^i \cdot SF_i \leq F_A^i \quad (1)$$

L_{design}^i : Loads as defined in the applicable Rules for load case i

SF_i : Safety factor associated with load case i

F_A^i : Characteristic failure load of a representative set of tests performed at most severe temperature under the testing configuration i .

The characteristic failure load obtained by testing, which is given for a specific level of confidence, represents the level of load below which a small proportion of specimens are expected to fail. It can be expressed as (2):

$$F_A^i = F_{average}^i - k_N S^i \quad (2)$$

with:

$F_{average}^i$: Average failure load of the tests in the testing configuration i

k_N : Coefficient function of the total number m of specimens tested in the configuration i for 5% characteristic value. The value of k_N is defined according to Table 5.

S^i : Standard deviation of failure load of tests in the testing configuration i .

Table 5. Value of k_N [3] as a function of the total number of considered tests for 5% characteristic value

N	3	4	5	6	8	10	20	30	infinite
k_N	3.37	2.63	2.33	2.18	2.00	1.92	1.76	1.73	1.64

3.2. Method B

Method B is dedicated to bonded assemblies with low qualification levels, Q1 and Q2. For instance, bonded assemblies presenting a proven and referenced maturity, integrated in a known environment and subject to loadings similar as the one for which the shipyard or the manufacturer has experienced, and for which it is to be documented.

Evidence that the assembly system complies with the above conditions are to be provided to the Society, as well as the description of the design methodology and its associated calculations.

In such case, recognized calculation models may be used as described in Appendix 4 of NR613 [1].

Strength is to be demonstrated for all load cases i and corresponds to the validation of the formula (3):

$$L_{design}^i \cdot SF_i \leq F_B^i \quad (3)$$

L_{design}^i : Loads as defined in the applicable Rules for load case i

SF_i : Safety factor associated with load case i

F_B^i : Predicted failure load as calculated by the applied design methodology for the load case i .

3.3. Method C

Method C can be applied for all qualification levels. The strength of the bonded assembly is to be demonstrated by adjusting predicted results from design methodologies with the help of a strength test campaign. The output of method C is the correlated failure load F_C^i obtained by evaluating the experimental sensitivity of the joint to design parameters and the robustness of the design methodology.

The overall process of this method is to:

- perform an experimental campaign at small to medium scale only

- model these tests using an appropriate design methodology
- determine the correlated failure load of these tests applying formulas based on EN1990:2003 [3]
- determine the correlated failure load for design load case using only the design methodology and applying the factors determined at previous step.

The design is to be validated in all most severe loading conditions i by confirming the following formula (4):

$$L_{design}^i \cdot SF_i \leq F_C^i \quad (4)$$

L_{design}^i : Loads as defined in the applicable Rules for load case i

SF_i : Safety factor associated with load case i

F_C^i : The correlated failure load for the load case i as determined by method C.

The strength testing campaign must be representative of the actual bonded assembly design, considering parameters such as substrate materials and stiffness, adhesive properties, adhesive thickness, edges, boundaries and loading conditions. To perform strength tests, the manufacturing of test specimens must replicate actual conditions, as results can be significantly impacted by manufacturing parameters. These conditions must be clearly defined and documented in the bonding specification. Any potential changes to the manufacturing process during qualification phases should be evaluated and accounted for.

The strength assessment should involve a minimum of 4 representative test setups to investigate the design envelope, including variables such as temperature, thickness, overlap, and loading type. Each defined test setup should be tested with at least 5 specimens. If large-scale specimens are tested, they should be included in the test database; however, the primary objective of large-scale testing is to confirm the design and manufacturing parameters simultaneously. The number of specimens may be reduced if a large-scale test setup is employed.

The loading speed during strength tests should match the order of magnitude of the actual loading conditions. The test plan must be agreed upon with the Society in charge of the certification.

The specimens may be instrumented as precisely as possible to enable cross-comparison of results with models, facilitate better understanding, and validate numerical models. The failure load should be recorded for each specimen (k) of the test setup (j), denoted as $F_{exp_k}^j$. The test data may reveal multiple failure modes, which should be clearly defined, recorded, and treated independently. A graph should be created with the predicted failure loads F_{pred} from the design methodology plotted on the horizontal axis and the experimental failure loads F_{exp} on the vertical axis. The j or k indices refer to the abscissas and ordinates, respectively.

By comparing the experimental data to the perfect resistance model, represented by a curve with a 1/1 ratio slope, see Figure 3, the robustness of the design methodology can be assessed. Two types of dispersion may be identified: experimental scattering, represented by the vertical spread of each group of data points, and limited accuracy of the design methodology, indicated by the misalignment of the group of data points.

Predicted results are adjusted to match experimental results by applying a constant ratio corresponding to the slope of the best linear fit line calculated using the least squares method between experimental and predicted failure loads. The slope of this best linear fit is denoted as “ b ” (5).

$$b = \frac{\sum_j [F_{pred}^j \cdot \sum_k F_{exp_k}^j]}{\sum_j [n_j \cdot (F_{pred}^j)^2]} \quad (5)$$

n_j : Number of specimens in the test set-up j

F_{pred}^j : Predicted failure load of test set-up j calculated with the design methodology chosen

$F_{exp_k}^j$: Failure load for each specimen k of the test set-up j

The use of a corrected model enables to make further error evaluation without considering a proportionality error in the model. Figure 3 illustrates this, as the model, in this case, is systematically predicting a lower strength than experimentally measured. The error between the corrected model and the experimental results is therefore minimized and represents the actual experimental dispersion and the model error in predicting the impact of a change in the design parameter.

For each specimen k of the test set-up j , the error δ_k^j can be expressed as follows (6):

$$\delta_k^j = \frac{F_{\text{exp}_k}^j}{F_{\text{pred}}^j \cdot b} \quad (6)$$

The use of the natural logarithm of this ratio (7) enhances the weight of the non-conservative results so that the error is majored when the result is non-conservative:

$$\Delta_k^j = \ln(\delta_k^j) \quad (7)$$

The average log of the ratio (8) is:

$$\bar{\Delta} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_j \sum_k \Delta_k^j \quad (8)$$

N : Total number of tested specimens whatever the test set-up

The variance (9) is to be considered as follows:

$$s_{\Delta}^2 = \frac{\sum_j \sum_k (\Delta_k^j - \bar{\Delta})^2}{N - 1} \quad (9)$$

The Coefficient of Variation, COV (10), is to be taken as:

$$COV = \sqrt{\exp(s_{\Delta}^2) - 1} \quad (10)$$

Using COV , the correlation coefficient β_C (11) of the assessed joint j is to be estimated through:

$$\beta_C = (1 - k_N \cdot COV) \quad (11)$$

k_N : Coefficient function of the total number N of specimen tested across all configurations for 5% characteristic value. The value of k_N is defined according to Table 5. As per EN1990:2003 [3], the selection of k_N depends on the knowledge of the COV associated with the basic variables. In the case of bonded assemblies, it is difficult to estimate the coefficient of variation for all the parameters involved in the joint, such as materials, material processing, surface preparation, application condition, environmental factors during application, etc. Therefore, it is recommended to use the table of k_N representing an unknown coefficient of variation of the various factors.

Figure 3 presents an example of an application case using Method C. In this case, the model systematically predicts lower results compared to the experimental tests, i.e., the best linear fit curve (green curve) lies above the perfect model curve (red curve). However, the correlated failure load curve (blue curve) is closer to the perfect model and falls below all the experimental results in this particular case.

Using β_C , the correlated failure load F_C^i (12) is to be determined using:

$$F_C^i = \beta_C \cdot F_{\text{pred}}^i \quad (12)$$

F_{pred}^j : Predicted failure load of load case i

Figure 3. Application case example of Method C [1]

4. Safety factors

Safety factors are specified based on the justification method A, B, C as defined previously. The safety factor SF (13) is considered as being the ratio between the characteristic failure load of the bonded assembly, depending on the justification method, and the maximal design load combination.

This ratio must satisfy the following conditions:

$$SF \geq \alpha \cdot C_t \cdot C_V \cdot C_F \cdot C_\theta \cdot C_b \quad (13)$$

α : Coefficient taken equal to:

- $\alpha = 1.5$ for method A
- $\alpha = 2.0$ for method B
- $\alpha = 1.5$ for method C

C_t : Safety factor considered for the failure criterion:

- $C_t = 1.2$ if failure criterion is determined by mechanical tests of the assembly (Method A or C)
- $C_t = 1.5$ if failure criterion is determined on the basis of data sheets for appropriate substrates (Method B)

C_V : Factor taking into account the ageing effect:

- $C_V = 1.2$ when joint considered as protected.

Note 1: When the joint is directly exposed to UV and/or water, the value of C_V can be adjusted by performing ageing tests.

C_F : Factor taking into account the bonding process and generally taken as:

- $C_F = 1.25$ in case of manual process
- $C_F = 1.15$ in case of a vacuum process, infusion, injection or equivalent

C_θ : Factor taking into account the temperature in service condition, to be taken equal to:

- $C_\theta = 1.0$ when the joint is tested in laboratory with the min/max temperature provided in service
- $C_\theta = 1.2$ when the mechanical characteristics of the joint at the min/max temperature provided in service are deduced from technical data sheets submitted by the adhesive supplier.

C_b : Factor taking into account the type of failure:

- $C_b = 1.0$ for ductile failure
- $C_b = 1.15$ for brittle failure or in absence of justification

When predicted failure load is determined by using a Finite Element Model in method B, SF can be reduced by 10%.

5. Application cases

This section presents three application cases, each illustrating one of the three justification methods. The first application involves a bonded mechanical fastener, the C-Claw S300 developed by Cold Pad [4] and recently certified by Bureau Veritas. The second application focuses on the bonding of stringers into the composite hull of sailing boats. The third application concerns the bonded connection of a wind propulsion system mast developed by Chantiers de l'Atlantique [7].

As the new rule note NR613 was published in February 2025, only the methodology to be applied for the qualification of the bonded assemblies is presented, neither test results nor numerical calculations are provided.

5.1. Bonded mechanical fastener

The C-Claw S300 is a non-intrusive fastener specifically designed for the maritime and offshore industry, offering an alternative to traditional welding, drilling and magnets. The fastener is engineered to withstand tension, and shear up to a regulatory load of 300 kg and utilizes a process-controlled installation, eliminating the need for hot work.

The C-Claw S300, see Figure 4, consists of a stainless-steel base plate that is bonded directly onto the metallic surface using a high-strength structural adhesive. From this base plate protrudes a threaded stud that allows components to be attached using nuts, bolts, or other standard hardware.

Figure 4. C-Claw S300 developed by Cold Pad

Although C-Claw S300 may be used for higher safety class, for the intended application as presented in Figure 5, and evaluated on a case-by case basis, the Safety Class is considered here as SC1 as the failure of the assembly will not affect an essential service of the vessel or will not lead to dangerous situation. The Maturity level of this application in marine and offshore is relatively new with some limited references, the associated Qualification Level is Q2.

Figure 5. Examples of C-Claw S300 applications [4]

As the design of C-Claw S300 is invariant, the materials used remained the same and the repeatable installation process is not varying for application, the justification Method A is fully applicable. In this context, Cold Pad performed a large experimental campaign in order to qualify C-Claw S300. Tensile and shear tests at different temperatures have been carried out, as well as 3 substrate thicknesses have been used in order to cover the maximum of realistic situations and also to assess the strength limits of the product.

Based on the testing campaign and the safety factor defined in 4, the bonded mechanical fastener has been qualified to sustain the regulatory capacity of 300kg in tension and in shear.

5.2. Stringers for composite hull

In general, stringers of composite sailing boats are premanufactured and bonded with a structural adhesive to reinforce the hull, as shown in Figure 6. The Maturity Level for this application is 1, indicating a proven technology. The failure of the bonded assembly could eventually affect or lead to a dangerous situation, resulting in a Safety Class of SC2. Consequently, the Qualification Programme to be applied is Q2. Such an assembly can be validated by using either an analytical calculation as detailed in Bureau Veritas rule note NR546 [5] or a Finite Element Analysis (FEA). The justification Method B based on calculation only is applicable.

Design rules loads are applied and the calculated stresses in the adhesive are compared with the breaking stresses provided by the adhesive supplier, considering the safety factor defined in 4. If criteria are not met in certain areas, the Classification Society may require laminating the stringers to reinforce the bonded assembly.

Figure 6. Composite stringers: Finite Element Model (left), prefabricated composite stringer positioning (middle) and hull with composite stringers (right) [6]

5.3. Wind propulsion system mast

Chantiers de l'Atlantique developed and manufactured SolidSail a full-scale prototype of a wind propulsion system. SolidSail is composed on a composite mast made in carbon fibre and a foldable rigid sail built in glass fibre panels mounted on a balestron able of rotating 360° or tilting up to 70° to pass under bridges. The main characteristics of this prototype are illustrated in Figure 7. The carbon fibre mast is produced in several section assembled together using a bonded sleeve system.

The bonded assembly is classified as a Safety Class SC3, meaning that the failure of the assembly will affect an essential service and could immediately lead to dangerous situations for human safety or for the safety of the ship. Since this solution is entirely new, the Maturity Level is 3, denoting an unproven technology. Consequently, the Qualification Level is Q5, the highest score. Q4 qualification requirements are mandatory, and the Classification Society may impose additional requirements.

Main characteristics:

- Height: 66 m,
- Width: 2 m,
- Weight: 20 tonnes
- Sail: 1,500 m²

Figure 7. SolidSail prototype, Chantiers de l'Atlantique [7]

As a full-scale mechanical test cannot be performed on the mast, and the Qualification Level exceeds Q2, the justification Method C is to be applied. An experimental and numerical campaign at small to medium scale specimens is to be performed. A minimum of 4 representative test setups is required by the Classification Society in considering varying parameters to cover the design variation.

For the development of this prototype, Chantiers de l'Atlantique carried out an extensive series of mechanical tests on small-scale samples, using various structural adhesives, adhesive thicknesses and designs. The experiments were simulated using different design methodologies: stress approach and stress-energy coupling approach as detailed in Appendix 4 of NR613 [1]. These results, combined with a full-scale model of the mast assembly, can be used to determine the correlation coefficient β_C and the predicted failure load F_{pred}^j to calculate the correlated failure load F_C^i . The bonded assembly is to be able of sustaining the applicable design rule loads multiplied by the safety factor, defined in section 4, while remaining lower than the correlated failure load.

6. Conclusion

The new Bureau Veritas Rule Note NR613 for Bonded Assemblies represents a significant advancement in the assessment and qualification of bonded structures for marine and offshore applications. Based on a qualification programme and three distinct justifications methods, NR613 should facilitate the wider adoption of bonded assemblies in shipbuilding and offshore structures.

The present paper demonstrated the practical implementation of these methods through three distinct case studies:

1. A bonded mechanical fastener, illustrating Method A (design justified by tests only).
2. Composite hull stringers, showcasing Method B (design justified by calculations only).
3. A wind propulsion system mast, exemplifying Method C (design justified by tests and calculations).

The implementation of NR613 by shipyards, design offices and Bureau Veritas Local Plan Office, in charge of the design review for the Class, will be crucial. Their experience and feedback should confirm the adaptability of the note and identify area for future improvements.

Future research will focus on the long-term performance of these assemblies, including the effects of ageing, fatigue, and creep, to further enhance the reliability and durability of bonded structures in marine environments.

References

- [1] Bureau Veritas NR613, Rule Note for Bonded Assemblies, 2025
- [2] D. A. Gross, "New DIN2304 standard and its use in practice," Adhesives & sealants, 2015.
- [3] Eurocode Basis of structural design EN1990:2003 Annex D "design assisted by tests
- [4] C-Claw S300, Technical datasheet,
https://www.cold-pad.com/files/ugd/e182d7_674699652d5f4ab0a452254380b9dc4c.pdf
- [5] Bureau Veritas NR546, Hull in composite, plywood and high density polyethylene materials, 2022
- [6] https://jp.scottbader.com/uploads/files/1023_stringer-bond-sep08-a3.pdf
- [7] <https://chantiers-atlantique.com/en/references/solid-sail-acoldrive/>